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The Factors Related to Anxiety in Workers with Covid-19 Exposure Risk in Banjarbaru City Health Centers

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ABSTRACT

The transmission of Covid-19 had a wide impact, including the health workers, which became the front line in order to help handling Covid-19 victims. Previous studies show that the health workers have 3 times bigger risk of being infected with Covid-19. This research aimed to know the determinant factors related to anxiety in workers with Covid-19 exposure risk in Banjarbaru City Health Center. The method used in this research is the analytical observational with the cross-sectional design at 10 health centers in Banjarbaru City on August 15th until September 15th 2022. The population in this research is the health workers of the health centers that handle Covid-19 in Banjarbaru City. The sample was taken by the simple random sampling method and obtained samples of 104 people who became the research respondents. All the data was taken by using an online questionnaire based on Google Forms and the anxiety parameter was determined by Hamilton Anxiety Rating Scale (HARS). The obtained Chi-Square test results show that family status ($p=0,034$), comorbid disease status ($p=0,034$), patient's honesty ($p=0,006$), PPE availability ($p=0,039$), knowledge ($p=0,035$), work load ($p=0,038$), and training ($p=0,047$) are related to anxiety, meanwhile, age ($p=0,129$) and sex ($p=0,570$) are not related to anxiety. The logistic regression test results show that comorbid status is the most influential variable that related to anxiety with the biggest Exp(B) value among the variables, which is 3,569. The research result gives recommendation that the Health Center, the Health Department, and other related parties must give a special attention to the health workers as the front line of Covid-19 handler, especially the health workers that have comorbid disease status, which needed the risk control in dealing very tense and anxiety-inducing conditions, and important to do anxiety management in order to not have negative impacts on the mental health of health workers.

KEYWORDS: Anxiety, Health Workers, Covid-19

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I. INTRODUCTION

The transmission of Covid-19 had a wide impact, including the health workers, which became the front line in order to help handling Covid-19 victims. Many health workers got exposed to this deadly disease and it made them must ready to live and die (Musyarofah et al., 2021). Previous studies show that the health workers have 3 times bigger risk of being infected with Covid-19, even though they live in a country with good Covid-19 management (Ashley et al., in Anggraini D, 2021). WHO estimated as much as 80.000 – 180.000 health and care workers could die because of Covid-19 during period range of January 2020 – May 2021, with convergence into intermediate scenario of 115.500 deaths. Based on the data released by laporcovid19, on February 14th 2022 there are records of 2.066 Indonesian health workers died fighting Covid-19.

A study conducted by Anggraini (2021) stated that there were 2.237 of 32.618 health workers or about 7% health workers were Covid-19 confirmed in South Kalimantan Province. Banjarbaru was the second highest district/city with Covid-19 exposure rate in women health workers is 70% after North Hulu Sungai (73%). Banjarbaru was also ranked in the top 5 of the most susceptible Covid-19 exposure to health workers, which was 7%. Furthermore, the amount of health workers who were exposed by Covid-19 was dominated by the hospital or health center workers, which was 2.005 of 2.237 people (90%). The big risk was in workers at health centers as the front line in handling Covid-19, besides doing the primary task inside a building, health center workers must do implementations of vaccination and Covid-19 surveillance, including testing, listing, and screening of Covid-19 patients or close contact group.

This matter surely caused concern and anxiety for the health workers, especially in Banjarbaru Health Centers that work hard in handling Covid-19, on one side they tried to fulfill their noble task according to their occupation oath, on the other hand they had to risk their life for the job. Not including the risk of Covid-19 exposure or carry the virus and expose it to their family at home. The anxiety itself is a feeling of fear where the external and internal stimulus causing unreasonable fear which disturbs the function of life. The external factors that can influence the anxiety in times of pandemic for the health workers are hour load in the hospital, personal relationship, financial problem, and other external factors, including illness and vulnerability of family members, or the negative stigma that can increase stress (Margaretha, 2020).

Anxiety management has a significant urgency, considering that anxiety is ranked first of mental issues among health workers, which dynamically can influence individual performance. As stated in the previous section, high level anxiety will cause excessive fear while working, even though the emotion usually will be accompanied by optimal, even excessive use of personal protective equipment (PPE), although sometimes this fear will cause health workers reluctant to accept, contact and treat Covid-19 confirmed patients (Apisarnthanarak, 2020). Furthermore, Fernandez R et al. (2021) stated that high level anxiety and depression often related to mental illness and other health problems because of impaired immunity due to unstable emotion which can lead to desperation and risk to end their life.

Based on the said background, it is important to conduct further research regarding the determinant of anxiety risk factors in workers with Covid-19 exposure risk in Banjarbaru City Health Center. This study will review the factors of age, sex, family status, comorbid disease status, patient's honesty, personal protective equipment's availability, knowledge, work load and training of workers in health facility, especially the workers of Banjarbaru City Health Centers.

II. MATERIAL AND METHODS

The method used in this research is the analytical observational with the cross-sectional design with comparative test using the Chi-Square test with 95% confidence level to determine the correlation between variables, which are age, sex, family status, comorbid disease status, patient's honesty, personal protective equipment's availability, knowledge, work load, and training with anxiety in workers at health facility, especially the workers in Banjarbaru City Health Center.

The population of this research is the workers with Covid-19 Exposure Risk in 10 Banjarbaru City Health Centers, which are Cempaka Health Center, Sungai Ulin Health Center, Sungai Besar Health Center, South Banjarbaru Health Center, North Banjarbaru Health Center, Guntung Payung Health Center, Guntung Manggis Health Center, Landasan Ulin Health Center, East Landasan Timur Health Center, and Liang Anggang Health Center. The workers are general practitioners, dentists, nurses, midwives, other health workers and supporting staffs based on decree/assignment letter of the Head of Health Center of 2022 that joined health worker resources of Covid-19, either that joined Rapid Movement Team of Covid-19 Transmission Prevention and Management, Swab Team, or Vaccination Team. The sampling method used in this research is the simple random sampling and 100 Health Center workers were obtained.

The instrument used in this research is an online questionnaire on Google Forms. The anxiety assessment used Hamilton Anxiety Rating Scale (HARS) with the categories of not anxious, if the score <14 and anxious, if the score ≥ 14 . The variables of age, sex, family status, and comorbid status were done by individual assessment according the current condition of respondents. The variable of patient's honesty was assessed by whether they have been handling patients with Covid-19 status that are unconfirmed and/or lead to Covid-19 symptoms while on duty as health worker resources in the last 7 days. The variable of PPE availability measured by self-assessment regarding the sufficiency of the personal protective equipment used by the respondents. The variable of knowledge measured by the understanding level of the respondents regarding the concept of Covid-19 (definition, transmission, and impact); path and safe work procedure in handling Covid-19; the procedure of confirmed patient or close contact of Covid 19, and the obedience and accuracy of PPE usage. The variable of work load measured by the work load level, either the obligatory duty (the task that must be done as an obligation of the work position or given by other parties) or the responsibility (one or a set of activities that were attached to a person and mandatory regarding the work position a person has) based on numeric rating scale in the last 7 days. The variable of training measured by whether a person got an official training regarding the work while on duty as Covid-19 health worker resources.

The data analysis used in the research is the univariate analysis to find out the distribution and frequency of each observed variable, the variables are anxiety, age, sex, family status, comorbid disease status, patient's honesty, PPE availability, knowledge, work load, and training. Then, the research used the bivariate analysis to analyze the correlation between each independent variable with dependent variable using the Chi-Square test with 95% confidence level.

III. RESULTS

The research data were collected by online questionnaire distributed to the respondents of 10 health centers in Banjarbaru City, which are Cempaka Health Center, Sungai Ulin Health Center, Sungai Besar Health Center, South Banjarbaru Health Center, North Banjarbaru Health Center, Guntung Payung Health Center, Guntung Manggis Health Center, Landasan Ulin Health Center, East Landasan Timur Health Center, and Liang Anggang Health Center.

Table 1. Frequency and distribution of respondents characteristics

No	Variable	Frequency	Percentage (%)
1	Sex		
	Male	16	15,2
	Female	89	84,8
2	Age		
	<35 years old	56	53,3
	≥ 35 years old	49	46,7
3	Family Status		
	Married	54	51,4
	Not Married	51	48,6
4	Comorbid Disease Status		
	Comorbid	33	31,4
	No Comorbid	72	68,6
5	Patient's Honesty		
	Patient is honest	32	30,5
	Patient is not honest	73	69,5
6	PPE Availability		
	Sufficient	75	71,4
	Not Sufficient	30	28,6
7	Knowledge		
	Good	71	67,6
	Enough	34	32,4
8	Work load		
	Excessive	57	54,3
	Not Excessive	48	45,7
9	Training		
	Have been trained	55	52,4
	Never been trained	50	47,6
10	Anxiety		
	Anxious	72	68,6
	Not anxious	33	31,4

Based on the table above, it is known that of 105 respondents, there are 56 respondents (53,3%) aged <35 years old. Most of the respondents are female, which are 89 respondents (84,8%), meanwhile, the male participants are 16 respondents (15,2%). Most of the participants are married, which are 54 respondents (51,4%), meanwhile, the participants who are not married are 51 respondents (48,6%).

The participants who do not have comorbid disease history are 72 respondents (68,6%). Most of the participants stated that there were patients who were not honest which are 73 respondents (69,5%), meanwhile, the participants stated that there were patients who were honest are 32 respondents (30,5%). The participants who stated that the PPE availability is sufficient are 75 respondents (71,4%), meanwhile, the participants who stated that the PPE availability is not sufficient are 30 respondents (28,6%).

Based on the univariate test results regarding the knowledge level, it is known that of 105 respondents, most of the participants have good knowledge level, which are 71 respondents (67,6%). The participants who are have been trained regarding their job as Covid-19 health worker resources are 55 respondents (52,4%). The participants who are anxious due to their job or other factors related to Covid-19 are 72 respondents (68,6%).

The bivariate test results that used the Chi-Square test are presented in the table below.

Table 2. Bivariate test result

Variable	Anxiety		Total	P-value
	Not Anxious	Anxious		
Age				
< 35 years old	14 (25%)	42 (75%)	56 (100%)	0,129
≥ 35 years old	19 (38,8%)	30 (61,2%)	49 (100%)	
Sex				
Male	6 (37,5%)	10 (62,5%)	16 (100%)	0,570
Female	6 (37,5%)	10 (62,5%)	16 (100%)	
Family Status				
Married	22 (40,7%)	32 (59,3%)	54 (100%)	0,034
Not Married	11 (21,6%)	40 (78,4%)	51 (100%)	
Comorbid Disease Status				
Comorbid	6 (18,2%)	27 (81,8%)	33 (100%)	0,048
No Comorbid	27 (37,5%)	45 (62,5%)	72 (100%)	
Patient's Honesty				
Not Honest	29 (39,7%)	44 (60,3%)	73 (100%)	0,006
Honest	4 (12,5%)	28 (87,5%)	32 (100%)	
PPE Availability				
Not Sufficient	5 (16,7%)	25 (83,3%)	30 (100%)	0,039
Sufficient	28 (37,3%)	47 (62,7%)	75 (100%)	
Knowledge				
Enough	6 (17,6%)	28 (82,4%)	34 (100%)	0,035
Good	27 (38%)	44 (62%)	71 (100%)	
Work Load				
Excessive	13 (22,8%)	44 (77,2%)	57 (100%)	0,038
Not Excessive	20 (41,7%)	28 (58,3%)	48 (100%)	
Training				
Never been trained	11 (22%)	39 (78%)	50 (100%)	0,047
Have been trained	22 (40%)	33 (60%)	55 (100%)	

IV. DISCUSSION

The research results stated that there is a significant correlation between anxiety with few risk factors, such as family status, comorbid disease status, patient's honesty, PPE availability, knowledge, work load and training. Meanwhile, there is no correlation between health worker's anxiety with age and sex.

A. Hubungan Antara Usia Pekerja dengan Kecemasan

The statistic result using the Chi-Square test is known that the p-value is $0,129 > 0,05$. The said matter shows that there is no significant correlation between the worker's age with anxiety. This correlates with the research of Alenazi et al. (2020), which said that the age does not affect the anxiety. This condition is understandable, even though higher anxiety can be felt by the younger age group, but the condition of Covid-19 pandemic was indeed a new thing for the health workers, in its correlation with age, whether the younger group or the older group has the same experience (Danu et al., 2021). Everyone also has different experiences in handling anxiety within themselves, regardless of age. If it correlates with the job, as health workers in Health Center service environment, whether young or old, has the same exposure risk in a situation that can induce anxiety without distinction.

B. Hubungan Antara Jenis Kelamin dengan Kecemasan

The statistic result using the Chi-Square test is known that the p-value is $0,570 > 0,05$. The said matter shows that there is no significant correlation between worker's sex with anxiety. This research correlates with the research conducted by Kaplale et al. (2021), which stated that there is no correlation between sex with health worker's anxiety level in Geser Health Center that handled Covid-19 patient. This condition is understandable considering the data from cross tabulation that stated the anxiety proportion, whether in male or female, is in the same condition. As health workers in the Health Center, there is no distinctive difference between work activities done by male or female, therefore, the situation exposure that can lead to anxiety can be experienced by both.

C. Hubungan Antara Status Keluarga dengan Kecemasan

The statistic result using the Chi-Square test is known that the p-value is $0,340 < 0,05$. The said matter shows that there is a significant correlation between family status with anxiety. This finding is quite different from previous studies, such as the on Fadli et al. (2020) did, which explained that anxiety occurs more in married health workers. This result is understandable because of 40 people are not married and in the category of anxious, 67,5% or 27 people

of those living with their parents and/or other families which generally older and riskier to exposed by Covid-19. The anxiety that the group felt is not related to their significant other, but rather their parents that live with them. This matter correlates with the research conducted by Danu et al. (2021), which the health workers who are not married but live with their family are more dominant in having anxious feeling than the ones who are not.

D. Hubungan Antara Status Penyakit Komorbid dengan Kecemasan

The statistic result using the Chi-Square test is known that the p-value is $0,048 < 0,05$. The said matter shows that there is a significant correlation between comorbid disease status with anxiety. The result of the questionnaire review obtained that the health workers who have comorbid disease have anxiety and fear if got exposed with Covid-19, because they understand the impact that may occur will worsen their comorbid disease, adds with the information related to deaths by Covid-19 on the comorbid disease patient. Based on WHO reports, can be seen that 8 of 10 deaths occurred to an individual, at least one is a comorbidity, especially the ones who have disease of cardiovascular, hypertension and diabetes, but also with various chronic conditions, the same description has been delivered by WHO that the workers who are 41 - 50 years old experiencing severe anxiety (WHO, 2020).

E. Hubungan Antara Kejujuran Pasien dengan Kecemasan

The statistic result using the Chi-Square test is known that the p-value is $0,006 < 0,05$. The said matter shows that there is a significant correlation between patient's honesty with anxiety. This result indeed correlates with previous research, such as the one that Sofia and Juwita (2021) conducted, also Fadli et al. (2020) which stated that there is a correlation between patient's honesty with health worker's anxiety, but the research stated that anxiety occurs more in patients that honestly stated their signs, symptoms, and status of Covid-19. But this condition is understandable, the obtained result from the research instrument shows that the situation where the patient explains the signs, symptoms, and status of Covid-19, in that time the health workers also felt the fear of the transmission risk. In few conditions, the health workers also overthink caused by the feeling of being not perfectly protected while in contact with the patients. Even though all the protocols are already implemented but the said condition more or less can cause anxiety in the health workers.

Patient's honesty still holds important roles related to anxiety in health workers. Besides that, patient's dishonesty in giving information to the health workers will risk to cause big problems and can

cause not only in one health worker, but can cause the transmission in a health facility visited by the patient (Riyanto, 2021).

F. Hubungan Antara Ketersediaan APD dengan Kecemasan

The statistic result using the Chi-Square test is known that the p-value is $0,039 < 0,05$. The said matter shows that there is a significant correlation between PPE availability with anxiety. This research result correlates with the research conducted by Fadli (2020), which the factor of PPE availability has impact in health worker's anxiety in effort to prevent Covid-19. This research result also correlates with the research conducted by Wenning et al. (2020). This condition is understandable, the research result stated that from the amount aspect, most of the health workers stated that the PPE is sufficient, but there are few respondents group that stated the PPE amount is not sufficient and 83,3% of them stated that the matter causes anxiety. The result of information processing from the questionnaire obtained finding that protective equipment, such as boots, goggles, masks, and HAZMAT that the amount is not enough. Protective equipment such as mask is already available at each Health Center and the respondents have already owned it, but due to the procedure that obligated mask change in certain duration, therefore, the available amount reduced a lot, so that often the availability was running low, even not available. When the condition occurs, not often the health workers do an initiative to longer the usage duration, buy independently or do a modification for the PPE so that it can give a safer feeling and can reduce the anxiety level (Wenning, 2020).

G. Hubungan Antara Pengetahuan dengan Kecemasan

The statistic result using the Chi-Square test is known that the p-value is $0,035 < 0,05$. The said matter shows that there is a significant correlation between knowledge level with anxiety. It is similar with the result of the research conducted by Danu (2021), knowledge has a significant correlation with anxiety. The information source regarding transmission, signs and symptoms, prognosis, medication, and mortality of Covid-19 which collected through various sources such as WHO and Health Ministry, social application, and mass media (Clin et al., 2020). The result of this research explains that 71 of 104 respondents are in the good knowledge category, and 34 among them have the enough knowledge. 88,2% among them (30 people) are health workers that helped in administrative work and field officer, also tracers. Most of the said category stated that they have understood well the definition, transmission, and impact of Covid-19, also the safe protocol, but sometimes confusion occurs in the management of confirmed patients, or close contact of Covid-19, where there was a time or condition in the

field that a little different with the things they understand. These differences made them not confidence in the knowledge they have. This condition also triggers their anxiety, anxious feeling that occurs because of the fear if the things they have done were not in accordance with the procedure or the condition where the challenge of Covid-19 exposure in themselves increases because of the offensive action done by the patients.

H. Hubungan Antara Beban Kerja dengan Kecemasan

The statistic result using the Chi-Square test is known that the p-value of $0,038 < 0,05$. The said matter shows that there is a significant correlation between work load with anxiety. This result correlates with the research conducted by Mattila et al. (2021), where the health workers stated that they were anxious and stress because of the increased work load during Covid-19 pandemic. Furthermore, the health workers who were stress regarding their increased job during Covid-19 pandemic have more anxiety than the workers whose stress levels do not increase (Matilla, 2021). The research result obtained information, where the health workers who are working in Health Center, beside bearing a job as a member of Covid-19 quick response team, also have another job and position. The activities such as patient monitoring, implementation, and vaccination target demands can increase anxious feeling in health workers. The anxiety of excessive work load can also impact someone's mental health, if their work load is heavy, therefore, it will tend to affect someone's mental or psychological state (Apriyanti F, 2022).

I. Hubungan Antara Pelatihan dengan Kecemasan

The statistic result using the Chi-Square test is known that the p-value is $0,047 < 0,05$. The said matter shows that there is a significant correlation between training with anxiety. The result of this research is understandable, training is an important thing to obtain because by attending the training, therefore, specific, and adequate information regarding Covid-19 can be obtained, and because of finding out the said information, then, the things that can cause anxiety can be manageable. In the opposite with the health workers who have never been in training, the information can only be obtained by self-looking and learning.

The result of this research correlates with the research conducted by Lestari et al. (2021), where the information and training have significant impact and most impactful correlation in anxiety level of the nurse during Covid-19 pandemic. The information regarding transmission risk and protection procedures against Covid-19 made the nurse capable to increase their awareness against disease and the said anxiety management procedures. An adequate training such

as the technique of PPE usage, protection system, practice standard, also patient safety and occupational safety are very important to give to all health workers who are also the front line in Covid-19 handling. The specific training and obtained information from the said training can help reduce anxiety and increase work trustworthy.

V. CONCLUSION

Based on the conducted research, generally can be concluded that the variables of family status, comorbid disease status, patient's honesty, PPE availability, knowledge, work load and training have significant correlation with the anxiety of the health workers who were the health worker resources of Covid-19 in Banjarbaru City, meanwhile, the variables of age and sex do not have significant correlation with the anxiety of the health workers who were the health worker resources of Covid-19 in Banjarbaru City. The results from this research give recommendation that the Health Center, Health Department and other involved parties must give special attention to the health workers as the front line in handling Covid-19, especially the variables that are correlated with anxiety.

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